

SOME FEATURES OF LEGAL TERMS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *Criteria for distinguishing types according to the form of words are different from structurally grouping of terms. Depending on the differences of the term from other lexical units, in particular, the fact that it can be formed on the basis of syntactic connection, and the units that make up the term also have a special meaning, groups of legal terms based their structural features are highlighted in the article.*

Key words: *enrichment of terminology, types of legal terms, explanatory dictionaries of Uzbek language, compound terms,*

The specific formal-structural structure of each language is also reflected in the enrichment of terms and terminology. In this study, by studying the structural description of legal terms (in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language), some ideas about the form of legal terminology, consisting of national and dialectal terms, are considered, suggestions and comments are made.

In particular, based on the very structural nature of the terms, it is possible to draw some conclusions about the ability of a terminological unit in the form of a word to contain a phrase or a whole sentence. This (structural specificity in term creation or formation) also proves the unique derivational aspects of language.

The terms differ from other units of the language system by the complexity of their structural structure. For example, in general lexicon, the use of compound units as independent noun units is rarely observed. Only in rare cases can we encounter such usages related to lexical spaces .

Legal terms that do not have the features of condensation, "recycling", such as common language units, occupy a significant place in the terminology of the legal field. The terms exist in the singular and often in the compound form, which is specific to a narrow layer.

For example, the right to fight torture, crimes committed by a group of individuals without prior conspiracy, individual items, endorsed encumbrances, less serious crimes, constitutional obligations of man and citizen, constitutional and legal status of man, human right to culture, financial responsibility liability for breach of antitrust law, copyright or invention rights, language sovereignty, grave contamination, unjust enrichment, and so on.

Similar terms can be called formally syntactically formed terms. This is because these terms represent a single concept in the form of a free combination of words. Legal terms such as the above are a form of active use in denoting a legal relationship and legal

status. Simplifying it in form can undermine the conceptual semantics of the term. Such terms also indicate the way in which a concept is expressed through its specific syntactic structure and its specificity.

Analytical approach to the classification of existing terms in legal terminology on the basis of their division into four (simple, compound, pair, repeated) groups - the analytical approach according to the traditional classification is the first stage of our work. When words are divided into types in terms of structural structure, they are often grouped according to the amount of stems, using terms such as simple, compound, double, repetitive, complex, compound, compound. Also, the fact that the terms belong morphologically mainly to the noun phrase shows that it is natural that there are also terms in the form of structurally abbreviated forms (some field terms have abbreviated terms).

The scientist R. Doniyorov, who has made a significant contribution to the development of sectoral terminology, carries out the formal-structural classification of terms in a unique way. According to him, terms consisting of more than one lexical member are terms formed syntactically. In Uzbek, as in other languages, terms created in this way are an important nominative source. In particular, in the technical terminology of the Uzbek language studied by the scientist, syntactically formed terms play a more important role than single-word terms.

Russian linguist A. Kozhin argues that "the sign of what is expressed in terms is expressed in such a way that they help to overcome the barrier of words in strengthening the social information in the process of cognitive action." Apparently, this opinion was the methodological basis for R. Doniyorov's conclusion .

In his research, R. Doniyorov divides syntactically formed technical terms into noun + noun, relative quality + noun, adjective + noun, process name + noun. The scientist also divided the terms in the form of noun + noun into type I isophagous, type II isophagous, type III isophagous. Such terms are evaluated as syntactically constructed terms in terms of their construction and as compound terms in terms of their structure.

There are some noteworthy aspects in the classification of technical terms made by R. Doniyorov. The scientist defines the patterns of terms formed by the syntactic method on the basis of morphological (for example, noun + noun), in some cases semantic (process name + noun) criteria. He also did not distinguish between such terms as belonging to the category of verbs. In general, the technical terms by the scientist are divided into such types as simple and compound.

In the process of structural classification, it is possible to distinguish between simple and common legal terms. The word "complex" is also used as a synonym for the word "joint" in the classification. But when we say complex term, we can understand not only form but also semantic complexity. In fact, when we say complex, we mean the amount of components. While any term consisting of more than one component is called

complex, compound terms are also included in the concept of complex term. But a compound term is a lexical combination of more than one word and the result is the formation of a single lexical unit.

For this reason, we think it is appropriate to use the term "complex term" in relation to terms formed by syntactic communication. The multi-component legal terms cited above (such as a family that has lost a breadwinner, a stateless person, a very serious crime) can serve as an example of a complex term.

The author of the work "Problems of scientific and technical terminology of the Uzbek language" N. Kasimov divided scientific and technical terms with more than one component into compound, pair and hybrid .

“Hybrid compound terms mainly involve related morphemes of Greek and Latin prefix character as international terminology. For example, the first components of hybrid compound terms (avia-, aero-, hydro-, ultra-) such as automotive, aerial photography, hydrothorax, ultrasound are such international terminology, and the second components are Uzbek words ” . In our opinion, the second component in hybrid terms is not always Uzbek words. For example, words such as industry, image, particle are units of assimilation layer.

There are also hybrid terms in the legal terminology of the Uzbek language: cybercrime, traffic, but these do not belong to the structural nature of the legal terms in the Explanatory Dictionary Of Uzbek Language, which we analyzed.

N. Kasimov's research also distinguished a pair of terms. According to him, “a word is a pair of terms, formed on the basis of equal connection of two independent lexical semantic components and expressing such meanings as generalization, plurality. The equality relationship between the paired parts is indicated by a hyphen in the text. In pronunciation, these parts have an equal phonetic peak, while at the same time uniting as a lexeme using a second single lexical stress ” . In the book, terms such as electron-optical, densifier-bar, tissue-knitwear, universal-chop are mentioned as a pair of terms. The pair of terms also exists, albeit to a lesser extent, in legal terminology: criminal procedure, judicial system, law enforcement agencies.

According to its components, complex terms are used in the form of "compound terms". Due to the ambiguity in the structure of the concept of "compound term" used to call these terms formed on the basis of syntactic connection under a common name, T. Valiev called it "structural-semantic features and lexicographic interpretation of Uzbek terms" (Ph.D., Ph.D.) and H. Mirzakhmedova, who studied the problem of structural structure and construction of transport terms in the Persian language, we can see that the term "compound term" was used .

Since the terms are a unit specific to a narrow layer and often exist in a compound form as above, legal terms can generally be divided into the following groups when studying structural features:

- 1) simple;

- 2) joint;
- 3) paired;
- 4) accumulative.

Among the legal terms included in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language (two-volume and five-volume), there are no units belonging to the above group of common terms due to their formal features. In the compilation of multi-volume annotated dictionaries, formal diversity should also be reflected as a factor reflecting the rich formal features of the language, and we therefore believe that joint legal terms should be included in the Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek Language.

“The lexical problem for any type of dictionary must be solved by an in-depth study of literary language and its methods. In this case, the issues of word formation and grammar, as well as the placement of artificial, compound, even and abbreviated words in the dictionary should be scientifically substantiated .

In the formal description of simple terms, whether it is primitive or artificial is of particular importance. By studying the views of scholars as to whether artificial words are linguistic or colloquial units, we support the idea that artificial words should be considered as linguistic units and that their interpretation in dictionaries should have a solid scientific basis. we look.

It should be noted that the interpretation of the meaning of primitive terms is more complicated than the interpretation of the meaning of artificial terms. This is because it is not difficult to interpret the meaning in terms of construction in terms of construction. Explaining which root words carry the terminological burden according to which sema as a term requires vigilance on the part of the researcher in adhering to the principle of conciseness of the dictionary article in multi-volume explanatory dictionaries.

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